

Solution equilibrium study on ternary oxovanadium(II)-hydroxyamino acids-imidazole systems

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Equilibrium study on the ternary VO^{II} : L-serine/L-threonine (AH₂) : imidazole(B) system in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ indicates the species $\text{VO}(\text{AH})$, $\text{VO}(\text{B})$, $\text{VO}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{VO}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{VO}(\text{A})(\text{B})$ and $\text{VO}(\text{A})(\text{B})(\text{OH})^-$. The involved functional groups of the various species are also indicated.

The work presented here describes a potentiometric investigation on the complete speciation in the complex formation in the binary vanadate : L-serine(A)/L-threonine(A) (1 : 1) and ternary vanadate : L-serine/L-threonine : imidazole(B) (1 : 1 : 1) systems in aqueous solution at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO_4 .

Results and Discussion

Mixed ligand complex formation equilibrium involving VO^{2+} , amino acid (A) and imidazole (B) in aqueous solution may be represented as

where, the stoichiometric q , r , and s integers are either positive or zero, and t is a negative integer for a protonated species, positive integer for hydroxo or a deprotonated species and zero for a neutral species. The β_{qrst} values were evaluated using SCOGS computer programme¹ and are presented in Table 1. Complex formation equilibria have been derived on the basis of distribution curves of the complexes occurring at different pH.

Binary complexes : The binary system consists of the general species $\text{VO}(\text{AH})$ and $\text{VO}(\text{B})$ along with some hydroxy species like $\text{VO}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{VO}(\text{OH})_2$ (Fig. 1). Degree of complex formation for the system $\text{VO}^{2+} + \text{L-threonine/L-serine}$ is greater than the VO^{2+} hydrolysis. Its formation starts from $\text{pH} > 4.5$. The major species $\text{VO}(\text{AH})$ probably corresponds to complexes with the R-COO⁻ group.

Ternary complexes : In the ternary system, the secondary ligand (i.e. imidazole) coordinates with binary complex at $\text{pH} \sim 5.0$. The major ternary species $\text{VO}(\text{A})(\text{B})$ is

present in maximum abundance (Fig. 1). This is supposed to exist in the 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{VO}^{2+} : \text{A} : \text{B}$ systems. The degree of complex formation for $\text{VO}^{2+} : \text{L-threonine/L-serine} : \text{imidazole}$ system are greater than the VO^{2+} hydrolysis.

Table 1. Protonation constants ($\log \beta_{\text{qrst}}$) and stability constants ($\log \beta_{\text{qrst}}$) of VO^{II} complexes

Temp = $25 \pm 1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO₄)

(a) Protonation constants :

Complex	L-Threonine	L-Serine	Imidazole
AH ₂	19.20	19.20	7.10
AH	10.10	10.10	-
BH ⁺	-	-	-
Stability constants :			
VO(AH)	10.86	10.67	-
VO(B)	-	-	5.77
VO(A)(B)	15.17	15.07	-
VO(A)(B)(OH)	-0.10	-0.10	-

EPR spectra : EPR spectra for the binary $\text{VO}^{2+} : \text{L-threonine/L-serine}$ and ternary $\text{VO}^{2+} : \text{L-threonine/L-serine} : \text{imidazole}$ were recorded as a function of pH. EPR parameters along the possible binding sites are presented in Table 2. The solution spectra are typical of monomeric oxovanadium(II) ($S = 1/2$, $I = 7/2$) species with no evidence for magnetic couplings between electron spins, i.e. line broadening or splitting in the spectral features. EPR spectra may help to elucidate the group that coordinates in equatorial position in solution. The spin Hamiltonian parameters were calculated following the reported method². The $g_{\parallel}$ and $A_{\parallel}$ values (Table 2) are in the range expected

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Table 2. EPR parameters and proposed equatorial coordination

Sl. no.	Composition	Complex	pH	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	$A_{\parallel}(G)$	$A_{\perp}(G)$	Proposed equatorial coordination	A_{zi}	
									Calculated value	Literature value
1.	$VO^{2+} : AH_2(1 : 1)$	$VO_{2+}^{2+} \text{ aq.}$	2.50	1.929	1.979	183	71	$4H_2O$	45.9	45.7
		$VO \text{ aq.}$	3.50	1.931	1.981	183	71	$4H_2O$	45.9	45.7
		$VO(AH)$	5.50	1.929	1.976	167	56	$R-CO_2$	42.7	42.7
								$R-NH_2$	40.1	40.1
								OH	38.5	38.5
2.	$VO^{2+} : AH_2 : BH(1 : 1 : 1)$	$VO \text{ aq.}$	2.50	1.929	1.980	183	70	$4H_2O$	45.9	45.7
		$VO(AH)$	5.00	1.926	1.975	167	58	$R-CO_2$	42.7	42.7
								$R-NH_2$	40.1	40.1
								OH	38.5	38.5
								H_2O	45.7	45.7
		$VO(A)(B)$	6.00	1.931	1.979	160	48	$R-CO_2$	43.1	42.7
								$R-NH_2$	40.5	40.1
								OH	38.9	38.5
								$=N-$	38.7	38.3

for the complexes with the present donor atoms³. At the lowest pH (i.e. 2.50), the EPR spectra of the binary and ternary systems show spectrum of only aquo $VO(OH)_5$ species having $g_{\perp} = 1.979$, $g_{\parallel} = 1.929$ and $A_{\parallel} = 183G$ and $A_{\perp} = 71G$. On increasing pH (3.50), the binary system shows slight decrease in $A_{\parallel}$ and $A_{\perp}$ values (Table 2). Similarly, the ternary system at pH (6.00) shows again slight decrease in $A_{\parallel}$ and $A_{\perp}$ values (Table 2) than the binary species $VO(AH)$. At this pH, the spectral features may comprise of two species $VO(AH)$ and $VO(A)(B)$. The different coordinated groups attached in the corresponding species are evaluated and these values along the literatures values are presented in Table 2. The binary species $VO(AH)$ has the coordinated groups, $R-COO^-$, $R-NH_2$, OH^- and H_2O , and ternary

species $VO(A)(B)$ has the coordinated groups $R-COO^-$, $R-NH_2$, OH^- and $=N-$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The standard solutions were prepared by using double-distilled water. Metal ion solutions were standardized by the usual procedure⁴. A CO_2 -free NaOH solution was prepared under N_2 -atmosphere. All solutions were made up to an ionic strength of 0.1 M ($NaClO_4$).

Potentiometric studies : Protonation constants of the ligands and stability constants of the vanadium(IV) complexes were determined in a 0.1 M ($NaClO_4$) at 25° by using a Systronics 335 pH-meter with a special glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. The general procedure for pH-metric titration was the same as described elsewhere⁵. The following sets of solutions were prepared (in total volume 50 ml) for titrations : (1) 0.03 M perchloric acid + 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, (2) 0.03 M perchloric acid + 0.003 M (A) + 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, (3) 0.03 M perchloric acid + 0.003 M (B) + 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, (4) 0.03 M perchloric acid + 0.003 M VO^{2+} + 0.003 M (A) + 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, (5) 0.03 M perchloric acid + 0.003 M VO^{2+} + 0.003 M (B) + 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, (6) 0.03 M perchloric acid + 0.003 M VO^{2+} + 0.003 M (A) + 0.003 M (B) + 0.1 M $NaClO_4$. Each of the above samples was titrated with 1 M NaOH.

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of $VO^{2+} : AH : B(1 : 1 : 1)$ system : (1) AH_2 , (2) AH , (3) BH^+ , (4) $VO(OH)^+$, (5) $VO(OH)_2$, (6) $VO(AH)$, (7) $VO(B)$ and (8) $VO(A)(B)$.

EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line century

Note

series spectrometer, equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band 100 kHz modulation. TCNE was used as field marker. The $g_{\parallel}$ and $A_{\parallel}$ values were measured according to the standard procedure⁶.

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References

1. I. G. Saycee, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397.
2. N. D. Chasteen in "Biological Magnetic Resonance", eds. L. Berliner and J. Reuben, Plenum, New York, 1981, Vol. 3, p. 53.
3. L. Casella, M. Gullotti, A. Pinter, S. Colonna and A. Manfredi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **144**, 89; A. J. Tasiopoulos, A. N. Troganis, A. Evangelou, C. P. Raptopoulou, A. Terzis, Y. Deligiannakis and T. A. Kabanos, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1999, **5**, 910.
4. I. M. Kolthoff, E. B. Sandell, E. J. Meehan and S. Bruckenstein, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", London, 1969.
5. K. B. Pandeya and R. N. Patel, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 602, 193; R. N. Patel, N. Singh, R. P. Shrivastava, S. Kumar and K. B. Pandeya, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2000, **89**, 207; R. N. Patel, H. C. Pandey, K. B. Pandeya and G. N. Mukherjee, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 850; R. N. Patel, R. P. Shrivastava, N. Singh, S. Kumar and K. B. Pandeya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 361; R. N. Patel, R. P. Shrivastava, N. Singh and K. B. Pandeya, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (India), Sect. A*, 2000, **70**, 133.
6. T. Vanngard in "Biological Applications of Electron Spin Resonance", eds. H. Swartz, J. Bolton and T. D. Borg, Wille-Interscience, New York, 1972, Chap. 9; B. G. Malmstrom and T. Vanngard, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1960, **2**, 118.